

INTERTEXTUALITY IN QUTLIBEKA RAHIMBOYEVA'S POETRY

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Abstract. This article will focus on intertextuality and its place in literature, its function, and in the work of the poet Qutlibeka Rahimboeva, one of the representatives of Uzbek literature, it will highlight its artistic significance, its expression and forms in poems, the importance of intertextuality in expressing the idea and purpose of creative fiction.

Key words: intertextuality in poetry, artistic text, intertextual dialogic communication, forms of intertextuality: image method, one-time gesture or direct quote

It is known that Intertextuality as a term was first introduced to the science in 1967 by the French structural researcher Y. Kristeva: "Intertextuality is a social whole that is considered as a single text expressed in the presence of connections between texts to express the general nature of texts."¹ According to him, any text is considered as a result of endless communication with other texts that are an integral part of the universal "cultural text", that is, as a sum of all printed texts that make up the cultural heritage. Y. Kristeva developed her concept of intertextuality in 1924 on the basis of revision of M. Bakhtin's work. "M. Bakhtin dwells on the laws of the existence of literature, every work reflects the reality of the creator, and is in regular dialogue with the literature of his predecessors and contemporaries. That is, he knows that the existence of literature has an intersubjective nature. And Y. Kristeva, who emphasized the formal side of M. Bakhtin's teaching, limits the dialogue to the scope of texts and brings intertextuality to the foreground instead of intersubjectivity."²

"Intertextuality appears in a literary text in various forms: intertextual communication is manifested in thoughts, in the form of imagery, in the form of a one-time allusion or direct quotation."³ There is a person who learns life from his surroundings, from nature, from the experience of his elders, observes, follows and imitates the existence of his environment.

¹ Kristeva Y. Bakhtin, words, dialogue and novel // French semiotics: From structuralism to poststructuralism / translation from French, comp., introductory article. G.K. Kosikova M: IG Progress, 2000. P. 27.

² Kuronov D. Dictionary of literary studies. - Tashkent. Academic edition, 2013.

³ Chotchaeva M., 2. Sosnovsky V. Postmodernism in the culture and literature of our time // Bulletin of ASU, 2017, No. 2. – Page 180.

Various forms of intertextual texts can be found in Uzbek literature and modern poetry. In particular, we will consider the forms of expression of intertextual texts in women's poetry, including the work of Qutlibeka Rahimboyeva, through the following examples:

*Ichkarida kimman men...
Dunyoni ko'raman asl rangida,
Jasorat qo'rquvni o'tadi yanchib.
Qochmayman nohaq-u haqning jangidan,
Tomoshabin emas, bo'laman jangchi.
Tashqarida kimman men...
Osmonni bilsa-da, yetmaydi boshim.
Zohirim mayishar turmaydi tikka.
Payg'ambar yoshidan o'tsa-da yoshim,
Sodiq xizmatkorman tirikchilikka.⁴*

This poem of the poetess was written based on the line "Ichkarida ham o'zim, tashqarida ham o'zim..." taken as an epigraph from one of the young poets, Jontemir Jondor. Poet Qutlibeka partially abandons the form in these lines and completely preserves the content. At the beginning of the stanza, he asks a rhetorical question, "Who am I inside..." and in the next four lines describes his inner "me". The next paragraph continues in the same way, only the rhetorical question is asked in the form of "Who am I outside..." and the answer is described through the next lines. It can be seen that in the lines, the lyrical hero is talking about his inner and outer "I" and not someone else. Summarizing the expression and content of the poem, we understand that the poetess wants to say "I am myself inside, I am also outside...".

On the example of the same poem by Qutlibeka, we will consider the next form of expression of intertextuality:

*Tashqarida kimman men...
"Baxt" so'zini aytaman hammadan ortiq,
"Baxt" so'zini aytaman hammadan oldin,
Daryoni sog'inib yotsa-da tuproq,
Holin so'ramayman, so'rayman oltin.⁵*

In this poem, the poetess contrasts her inner and outer self while comparing her inner self and her outer self. That is, the external "I" of the lyrical hero acts against the inner me, sometimes selfishly, even though he does not want to, due to the demands of the society and the socio-economic environment.

⁴ Qutlibeka. Lightning season. Sahhof, Tashkent. 2022. P.48

⁵ Qutlibeka. Lightning season. Sahhof, Tashkent. 2022. P.48

In order to express our opinion more clearly, below is an excerpt from the poet Shavkat Rahman's poem about the "Baxt so'zi":

*Bu so'zni bir umr aytmay yashadim,
Har shodlik kelganda yurdim sekinroq.
G'am so'zin elimdan avvalroq aytdim,
Baxt so'zin aytaman eldan keyinroq.*

Pointing to this poem by Shaukat Rahman, the poetess writes that she could not live like "the poets who sacrificed their lives for the happiness of the nation" as described by the poet, and could not sing for their people like them. Although the inner "I" is different, although each truth is seen in its own color, although it rebels a thousand times, this state does not come out. The lyrical hero of the poetess is an unhappy poetess, who said the word "Happiness" more than anyone else and before everyone else, and on the contrary, she herself did not feel or taste happiness. Although Shavkat Rahman used the word "Happiness" in this sense and style before the poetess, it is not mentioned anywhere in the poem. It is also clear that these two verses of the poem were written in imitation of the poet's poem.

*Nigohing chaqinli: boqmaysan yerga,
Chinga qarab yurdik chamadan, chendan.
Ishonch uyg'ondimi shoirga, she'rga,
Yor, qora ko'zlaring ne tilar mendan?..⁶*

This poem is also written without a title, and the intertext in the poem is taken from the epic. As you can see, it is not indicated by quotation marks or quotation marks. But the same verse is presented as an epigraph. Not only one sentence was copied from the epic, but also the tone and rhythm of this lyrical work were mastered.

The same type of intertextuality can be found in the works of the poetess Qutlibeka:

*Ko'zda yoshim munchoq-munchoq tizildi,
Ishq quvonchim jon-jonidan uzildi,
Yor ketgani qish zahridan sezildi,
Daryo, eshit kuyrab yotgan so'zimni,
G'amsuv sepib so'ldirma gul yuzimni.*⁷

Mazkur she'rning sarlavhasi "Zuhro o'tinchi", epigrafi esa, "Tohir va Zuhro" dostonidan olingan "Ko'zda yoshim munchoq-munchoq tizildi" jumlasidir. Bu jumla hech o'zgarishsiz she'rning ikki o'rnida, ya'ni shu jumla

⁶ Qutlibeka. Lightning season. Sahhof, Tashkent. 2022. P.48

⁷ Qutlibeka. Lightning season. Sahhof, Tashkent. 2022. P.14

bilan boshlanib, shu jumla bilan tamomlangan. Ammo bu she'rdagi intermatnda yuqoridagi she'r kabi iqtibos keltirilmasdan, sarlavha va epigraf bilan bu jumlagi ishora qilingan. Aslida bir belgi yoki ishoraning o'zi ham yetarli bo'lishi mumkin. Dostondan olingan bu jumla she'rda boshlanma vazifasini o'tagan.

The title of this poem is the epigraph "*Zuhro o'tinchi*" from the epic "*Tahir va Zuhro*" and the sentence "*Ko'zda yoshim munchoq-munchoq tizildi*". This sentence is unchanged in two places of the poem, that is, it starts with this sentence and ends with this sentence. But the intertext of this poem refers to this sentence with the title and epigraph, without citing it like the above poem. In fact, a sign or a sign may be enough. This sentence from the epic served as the beginning of the poem.

References:

1. Kristeva Y. Bakhtin, words, dialogue and novel // French semiotics: From structuralism to poststructuralism / translation from French, comp., introductory article. G.K. Kosikova M: IG Progress, 2000. P. 27.
2. Kuronov D. Dictionary of literary studies. - Tashkent. Academic edition, 2013.
3. Chotchaeva M., 2. Sosnovsky V. Postmodernism in the culture and literature of our time // Bulletin of ASU, 2017, No. 2. – Page 180.
4. Qutlibeka. Lightning season. Sahhof, Tashkent. 2022.

